

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17265659

Macroeconomic Variables and Stock Market Performance: A Time Series Study from Nigeria

Dr. Edward Chinedum Friday, Fipesa¹ & Ufomadu Ogechukwu Abel²

Accountancy Department, Ogbonnaya Onu Polytechnic Aba, Nigeria

¹E-mail: chinedumedward@gmail.com.

²Email: ogescot@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of macroeconomic variables on the performance of Nigeria stock market. Time series data were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin from 1990-2023. Stock market performance was modelled as the function of Real Gross Domestic Product, Interest rate, Inflation Rate, Broad money supply and Exchange Rate. After the unit root test found the variables are integrated in the order of 1(I), Error Correction model was adopted. The study found that 66.7% of the variations in stock market performance were explained by macroeconomic variables. Real gross domestic product have positive and significant effect on stock market performance, interest rate have positive but no significant effect, exchange rate have negative and significant effect on stock market performance while inflation rate and money supply have positive and no significant effect on stock market performance. From the findings, the study concludes that macroeconomic variables have mixed effect on stock market performance. The study recommends that the need to sustain the Central Bank's current exchange rate policies, which had resulted in the convergence of rates in the market. The recommendation was that there is the need for sensible coordination of macroeconomic policies in Nigeria. Policy a maker in Central bank needs to make such policies that help to stabilize the exchange rate. Sufficient level of money supply through appropriate monetary policy must be put in place in order to encourage stock market activities and consequently stock prices in Nigeria. Inflation control should be brought to a level where it becomes stock market enhancing and efficient exchange rate management should be adopted by government; which take into account the relevance of the stock market as a possible significant strong economical indices; when addressing the issue of exchange rate management and interest rates should be made to encourage investment in Nigeria, so as to enhance stock market returns.

Keywords: Macroeconomic Variables, Stock Market Performance, Time Series Study, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

The relationship between macroeconomic variables and stock market behavior has been extensively studied and documented in developed capital markets such as USA, Japan, Australia, Canada and European countries. Notable among them is one by Kimani & Mutuku, (2023) on the US stock market, which set the tone for a series of recent studies within the Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT) framework. Most of these studies relate to US and Japanese stock markets (Kumar, 2024). Fama (1981) reported a positive relationship between stock returns and macroeconomic variables. In spite of increasing migration of capital from developed market to emerging markets and associated high returns, (Martinez-Moya, Ferrer-Lapena, &Escribano-Sotos, 2023) and Osinubi (2004) emerging stock markets in developing countries like Ghana have not been well studied. In 2006 foreign equity accounted for 75.3% of the equity finance recorded in Ghana compared to 29.9% in 2001 according to Ghana investment promotion centre

quarterly report. The growing interest and the performance of emerging markets have been attributed to the conduct of sound macroeconomic policies, privatization, stock market reforms and financial liberalization.

Nigerian Capital market was established in 1960 for the purpose of bridging savings and investment gap and simplifies the sourcing long term fund. It constitute a network of financial institutions and investors interact to mobilize and allocate long term funds to productive investment and funds are exchanged for financial assets issued by borrowers or traded by stock holders which in turn offers access to a variety of financial instruments that enable economic agents to pool, price and exchange risk (Akani & Imegi, 2017). The Nigeria capital market is classified among the emerging financial market of world and one of the fast growing in Africa (Anyamaobi, 2018). The performance of Nigeria capital market can be measured in term of number of listed companies; number of listed securities; size of the market or market capitalization and all-share price index. According to stock market reports 2019, there are 161 companies quoted on the floor of the exchange, market capitalization of listed domestic companies as percentage of gross domestic products in Nigeria was reported at 9.8 per cent in 2019 while all share decreased 1639 points or 6.10 per cent since the beginning of 2020. The above shows that the performance of the Nigeria capital market has fluctuated over time. Nigeria financial market has undergone various reforms with the objective of repositioning the market for inflow foreign portfolio investment and to stop capital flight from the Nigeria. Financial market reforms are predicted upon the need for reorientation and repositioning of existing status quo in order to attain an effective and efficient financial market that accommodates domestic and foreign investors. The financial sector reforms include deregulation of interest rates, exchange rate, entry/exit into the banking business, establishment of the Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) strengthening the regulatory and supervisory institutions, upward review of capital adequacy, sectorial credit guidelines, capital market deregulation and the introduction of direct monetary policies instruments (Nnanna, Englama & Odoko, 2004).

There is a widespread belief that the stock market is sensitive to announcements of economic events. Reports of stock prices falling because of disappointing financial and macroeconomic figures or rising due to encouraging news on the inflation front is commonplace in the financial media (Akani, 2013). While such market behavior is consistent with standard finance theories that suggest that rate of return on an asset is determined by systematic economic news while no extra reward can be earned for diversifiable risk, there exists a large gap in the empirical identification of the state variables determining asset pricing. Indeed, despite the strong association as suggested by the press between movements in stock prices and macroeconomic announcements, there has been relatively scanty hard evidence to support the belief that stock prices respond to general macroeconomic news apart from some types of monetary information most especially the developing countries with emerging financial markets (Aduda, Masila, & Onsongo, 2022).

Arouri, Lahiani and Nguyen (2024) stated of the information asymmetries is important reason for the failure to capture the impact of macroeconomic news on stock prices is that standard regressions treat the market reaction to the same type of macroeconomic news as being identical at all times. The market, however, seems to treat otherwise similar macroeconomic information differently, depending on the stages of the business cycle or the states of the economy. Take the release of data on industrial production as an example. During a recession, a surprising pick-up in industrial production could be interpreted by market participants as indicating a recovering economy and an improved outlook for corporate earnings and thus might cause a stock market rally. Inflation surprises could also affect the financial market through channels other than changes in inflationary expectations. Unanticipated higher inflation may lead to the expectation of more restrictive monetary policies, which in turn will lead to the reduced cash flows and lower stock prices. A positive inflation surprise could also induce agents to adjust their savings, resulting in higher interest rates and lower stock prices. In any event, all these potential links suggest that surprises in inflation announcements could be positively related to interest rates and negatively related to stock prices.

There are two prominent competing explanations for the role of monetary news in affecting the stock market. The first hypothesis is the policy anticipation effect (or the liquidity effect), which says an unanticipated expansion of the money supply might lead market participants to expect the central bank to tighten in order to offset the increase, which will result in higher real interest rates in the future. The second one, the inflation expectation effect, postulates that a positive shock in the money supply leads to an upward adjustment of inflation expectations, which in turn leads to higher nominal interest rates. Both hypotheses lead to the same effect of monetary information on stock prices. If interest rates, and hence stock prices, respond to money supply announcements because of inflationary expectations, they should also be affected by shocks contained inflation rate announcements. A negative effect should emerge if a positive surprise in announced inflation induces agents to raise their level of expected inflation.

According to the “Fisher effect” expected nominal rates of interest on financial assets should move one-to-one with expected inflation (Fisher, 1930). Moreover, changes in both short-term and long-term rates are expected to affect the discount rate in the same direction through their effect on the nominal risk-free rate (Kimani & Mutuku, 2023). Some previous studies have reported that it is not interest rate itself that is relevant but the yield and default spreads that are more likely to influence equity returns. Josiah and Akpoveta (2019) examined the influence of key macroeconomic variables on stock market returns in Nigeria, Karki (2018) empirically examined the macro-economic factors of the stock market performance in Nepal, Lionel, Alfa and Samuel (2020) examined the impact of capital flight on domestic investment in Nigeria between 1980 and 2017. From the above, this study examined the effect of macroeconomic variables on stock market performance in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Macroeconomic Variables

Macroeconomic variables are indicators or main signposts signaling the current trends in the economy. Like all experts, the government, in order to do a good job of macro-managing the economy, must study, analyze, and understand the major variables that determine the current behavior of the macro-economy.

Exchange Rate

Exchange rate is the value of one currency for the purpose of conversion to another. Exchange rate movements greatly affected the stock market return volatility owing to its information content to the investors. When there are high fluctuations in the exchange rates, the exchange rates movement, there would be high movements of market return volatility. Some studies have concluded that there is a strong relationship between exchange rate movement and stock market returns volatility, while others have not. Specifically, the information content of exchange rate movement would be carried to the securities business.

The U.S. dollar and the Euro are the most traded currencies in the world (BIS, 2013). It has become as main sources for international transactions. On January 2002 the Euro became official and after the introduction the Euro appreciated against the Dollar. Important determinants of the exchange rate are the demand and supply for the currency, inflation, interest rate and the economic and political risk (Shapiro, 2013, Lipsey & Chrystal, 2007). Due to the wide worldwide usage the U.S. dollar and the Euro are accepted as the most important exchanges currencies. Many academics examine the relationship between exchange rate and stock performance for both theoretical and empirical reasons. This paragraph will present the theoretical linkage between exchange rates and stock performance followed by the empirical evidence about this relation. The large increase in the world trade and capital movements have made the currency value as one of the important factors that influence business profitability and equity prices (Kim, 2003). Exchange rate fluctuations affect the international competitiveness of companies, considering their influence on import and export prices. It influences the value of the company since the future cash flows change together with the fluctuations in the currency values. Economic theory suggests that fluctuations in exchange rates will result in a change in the investments and profitability, reflected in the financial performance.

Consequently, movements in the company’s operations affect stock returns (Agrawal, Srivastav & Srivastava, 2010). The earlier and frequently cited study by Dornbusch and Fisher (1980) indicate the

same with a flow oriented model. They argue that depreciation in the local currency improves the competitiveness of domestic companies and their exports and future cash flows. This will result in increasing stock prices, as a response to the rise in expected cash flows. Conversely, an appreciation in the local currency will decrease the foreign demand of an exporting company. This will lead to a decline in the profit, as would the stock returns. Consistently, for an importing company the sensitivity of the firm value to currency value fluctuations is just the opposite (Yau & Nieh, 2006). Establishing the relationship between stock prices and exchange rates is important for a few reasons. First, it may affect decisions about monetary and fiscal policy. Gavin (1989) shows that a booming stock market has a positive effect on aggregate demand. If this is large enough, expansionary monetary or contractionary fiscal policies that target the interest rate and the real exchange rate will be neutralized. Sometimes policy-makers advocate less expensive currency in order to boost the export sector. They should be aware whether such a policy might depress the stock market. Second, the link between the two markets may be used to predict the path of the exchange rate. This will benefit multinational corporations in managing their exposure to foreign contracts and exchange rate risk stabilizing their earnings.

Inflation Rate

The effects of inflation on the economy are diverse and can be both positive and negative. The negative effects are however most pronounced and comprise a decrease in the real value of money as well as other monetary variables over time. As a result, uncertainty over future inflation rates may discourage investment and savings, and if inflation levels rise quickly, there may be shortages of goods as consumers begin to hoard out of anxiety that prices may increase in the future.

One of the most important questions that arise in the assessment of equity markets is the correlation between stock prices and inflation. It is commonly believed that rising prices also push up corporate profits and hence share prices. But is this fact or fiction? To evaluate the impact of inflation on stock market price, investors frequently draw on experiences in the immediate aftermath of the two World Wars. In Europe, these periods were marked by drastic currency depreciation. However, stockholders at the time were far less affected by inflation and currency reforms than were (for example) holders of fixed-income securities or cash, some of whom lost all of the money they had put up.

When inflation is rising, a restrictive monetary policy squeezes corporate sales potential. Furthermore, inflation affects market participants' economic activities. It generates risks for nominal contracts such as loans, pensions and pay settlements. Long-term contracts, such as investment financing or collective pay agreements which run for a number of years, are exposed to the risk that one of the parties to the agreement might inadvertently be placed at a disadvantage. In this kind of environment creditors demand risk premiums – with all the consequences this has for the cost of capital. Market players become less willing to commit to long-term contracts. Instead, they plan and act in shorter timescales. This requires extra resources, which may make sense from the individual's point of view but which are nonetheless misplaced in macroeconomic terms. This means that options designed to put resources to efficient economic use options which are pursued in periods of low inflation are not exploited. In other words, an inflationary economy forfeits growth potential.

In the meantime, the negative impact of inflation on stock performance is widely recognized in the empirical literature. An exception to this is the article by Boudoukh and Richardson, (1993). Looking at the unusually long horizon of the years 1802-1990, the authors conclude that inflation and (rolling) five-year returns move broadly in parallel. Furthermore, international comparative studies show that stock prices can benefit from inflation as soon as the inflation rate rises above around 15 percent. Clearly, there is a flight to money and near money assets in times of hyperinflation. This is the conclusion reached using the Gordon approach, which argues that, if a stock is fairly valued, the inverse P/E ratio will correspond to the sum of the real return and the risk premium minus the average (real) profit growth rate per share.

Money Supply

Money supply refers to the total amount of money in circulation or in existence in a country. There are several standard measures of the money supply, including the monetary base, M1, and M2. The monetary base is defined as the sum of currency in circulation and reserve balances (deposits held by banks and other depository institutions in their accounts at the Federal Reserve).

Money supply represented by M2 in our study measures the degree of liquidity in the economy and any change in it is likely to influence the investment decisions of both individual and institutional investors. A study by Pearce and Roley (1985) argues that unanticipated announcements in monetary policy have a significant impact on stock prices while Jain (1988) documented that announcements about money supply and consumer price index are significantly associated with stock price changes. Boyle (1990) suggests that changes in monetary uncertainty modify the stock prices risk premium to replicate the added expected prices that investors demand for assuming the risk of keeping stocks. In this way, monetary uncertainty is supposed to depict a negative association with stock prices. The relationship between money supply and the stock market has been investigated empirically. Cheng (1995) and Groenewold (1997) showed that money supply affects stock market performance.

Interest-Rate

Interest rate is one of the important macroeconomic variables, which is directly related to economic growth. Generally, interest rate is considered as the cost of capital which means the price paid for the use of money for a period of time. From the point of view of a borrower, interest rate is the cost of borrowing money (borrowing rate). From a lender's point of view, interest rate is the fee charged for lending money (lending rate). Good investors always look for investing in an efficient market.

In an inefficient market few people are able to generate extra ordinary profit which causes loss of confidence of the general people about the market. In such cases, if the rate of interest paid by banks to depositors increases, people switch their capital from share market to bank. This will lead to decrease the demand of share and to decrease the price of share and vice versa. On the other way, when rate of interest paid by banks to depositors increases, this in turn will force lending rate to increase. Increase in lending rate leads to decrease the level of investment in the economy which is also another reason of decreasing share price and vice versa. So, theoretically there is inverse relationship between share price and interest rate.

Governments or monetary authorities have several tools of monetary policy. The interest rate is one of them and is used in order to influence the economy. A high interest rate is an indication of a tight monetary policy. In times with high interest rates, it is more costly for firms to borrow which makes it more unattractive to invest. Not only firms, but also individuals are affected by high interest rates, since the repayments of their loans and mortgages will be cost more. Therefore, high interest rates tend to decrease demand, while low interest rates stimulate demand in the economy (Lipsey and Chrystal, 2007). Interest rate fluctuations are worldwide acknowledged as an important source of uncertainty for firms. Graham and Harvey (2001) provide evidence that fluctuations in the interest rate are the second most significant risk factor for companies. They mention the maturity match between assets and liabilities as 'important or very important'. The influence of the interest rate on the stock performance of firms has received big attention in empirical studies, yet a lot of these studies focused on financial institutions due to the particularly interest rate sensitivity of these sector Kasman et al., 2011; Memmel, 2011).

Real Gross Domestic Product

Real Gross Domestic Product (real GDP) is a macroeconomic measure of the value of economic output adjusted for price changes (i.e., inflation or deflation). This adjustment transforms the money-value measure, nominal GDP, into an index for quantity of total output. The effect of GDP on equity prices is difficult to predict in part because there are two potentially offsetting effects. Stronger than expected GDP growth implies potentially stronger dividend growth and higher equity prices, however, the accompanying inflation and interest rate concerns tend to have a negative effect on equity prices. Several studies in the macroeconomics and finance literature have examined this question with sufficiently large datasets to allow for more rigorous methods. These studies test for the effect of the surprise component of various macroeconomic releases (i.e. actual less consensus or survey estimates) on asset price movements on that day, or intraday around the time of the release. See for example Bernanke and Kutter (2003) and Fair (2003). In general, these studies tend not to find a significant effect of the GDP release news and equity price movements due to the offsetting effects noted above and difficulty measuring the true "news" contained in the data release. Nevertheless, the disconnect between equity prices and GDP release surprises remains a puzzle. A recent study by Rigobon and Sack (2006) tries to address some of these

problems. Using data from 1994 to 2006, they find no significant effect from advance GDP release surprises on equity prices using a standard OLS regression. However, they do find a slightly positive effect that is statistically significant when they use a more advanced econometric method which controls for censoring effects. The coefficient was tiny, so it would take a large surprise to generate even a small movement in stock prices according to their findings.

Stock Market Performance

The efficiency of a nation's security market is used to monitor and evaluate the performance of its economy. The stock market index is the gauge to determine the stock market performance. As (Yardi & Adjasi, 2007), posited World Bank, IMF, and ADB use stock market performances to evaluate countries' economic growth to undertake development programs in emerging markets. Liquidity is used to refer to the ability of investors to buy and sell securities easily. It is an important indicator of stock market development because it signifies how the market helped in improving the allocation of capital and thus enhancing the prospects of long-term economic growth. This is possible through the ability of the investors to quickly and cheaply alter their portfolio thereby reducing the riskiness of their investment and facilitating investments in projects that are more profitable though with a long gestation period. Two main indices are often used in the performance and rating of the stock market: total value traded ratio; and turnover ratio.

Theoretical Review

Stock Market Chaos Theory

The hypothesis of Stock Market Chaos proposes that complex frameworks inside the arbitrary nature of chaos display basic designs, interconnects, criticism circles, reiteration, self-similarity, fractals, and self-organization. Within the setting of this study, this hypothesis holds pertinence as its defenders argue that cost is the ultimate perspective to alter for a stock, bond, or any other security. Thus, periods of small cost instability may not fundamentally reflect the genuine state of the market's well-being. During the research on chaos, the financial markets, and symmetry, using this theory, inferred financial markets, rife with randomness as they are, contain variables of determination that can be identified and used reliably in many cases for prediction posits (Han Do, 2023). Research work carried out by (Cohen, 2022), while comparing the chaos hypothesis and the productive market theory in measuring stock market performance, found authentic market crashes, such as the European Tulip rage of the 1500s. Modern-day universal stock market crashes may dependably be proven through cash supply circles inside the economies. In a study conducted by (Diaz, 2021) that examined the returns of currency exchange exchanged notes using the chaos theory, it was concluded that the volatilities of currency 13 exchanges exhibit properties of long-memory, non-stationarity, and non-inevitability. Soros, (2019), using the chaos theory on the behavior of money supply patterns and stock performance, concluded that money supply & time are necessary factors when speculating and observing stock market behaviors before, during, and after the period of the chaos.

Arbitrage Pricing Theory

Ross formulated the Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT) in 1976. According to this theory, the relationship between assets and independent macroeconomic indicators defines the arbitrage pricing relationship. Additionally, the APT recognizes that the overall value of a firm is influenced by a risk-independent component. The theory is pertinent to this research since it has been shown in earlier studies that stock market performance can be predicted using a time series of predictor factors, with economic variables being one of such variables. By analyzing the impacts of macroeconomic factors, it gets to be attainable to decide the quality, nature, and scope of the relationship between macroeconomic components and stock market performance. The application of the arbitrage pricing hypothesis in this analysis is useful because it empowers an examination of how macroeconomic variables particularly impact the performance of the NXG share index.

Macro Variable Model

The macro variable version of the Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT) uses observed factors assuming that stock prices react to news about macroeconomic and financial variables. Following the pioneering work

of Chen *et al.*, (1986), there has been significant work in the literature. These works confirmed that stock market return is affected by macroeconomic and financial variables. As most recent studies used this framework, it is important to first understand the true factor structure of this study.

According to Chen *et al.*, (1986), economic state variables have systematic effects on stock returns. From the perspective of the efficient market hypothesis and rational expectations, asset prices should depend on their exposures to the state variables that describe the economy. Chen *et al.*, (1986) correlated various macroeconomic variables with returns on five portfolios. They found that four macroeconomic variables were significant: Industrial production; Unanticipated inflation; Twists in the yield curve; and Changes in risk premium (spread between low grade bonds and high grade bonds).

Chen *et al.*, (1986) chose a set of economic state variables as candidates for sources of systematic asset risk. Several of these economic variables were found to be significant in explaining expected stock returns. The authors did not completely investigate the significant macroeconomic variables but selected some variables that showed some significance compared to other possible macro variables. Beenstock and Chan (1988) presented a study proposing an alternative methodology for testing Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT) in the context of the market for British securities. Using the macro variable model, they identified four macroeconomic variables for the UK market: Interest rates; Fuel and material costs; Money supply; Inflation. The arbitrage pricing theory (APT) with macroeconomic factors, put forward by Chen *et al.*, (1986), was tested by Groenewold and Fraser (1997) using monthly Australian sectoral share-price indexes for the period 1980-1994.

Empirical Review

Josiah and Akpoveta (2019) examined the influence of key macroeconomic variables on stock market returns in Nigeria. In-depth knowledge of the relationship between macroeconomic variables and stock market returns is essential in designing an effective policy framework for managing volatile macroeconomic variable indices like capital flows, inflation, money supply, interest rate, exchange rate fluctuations and their disruptive potential. We utilized cointegration Tests, the error correction model mechanism and Granger causality tests to show the nature of relationship amongst the variables of interest, with stock market returns serving as our dependent variable. The empirical findings show that sound macroeconomic environment reflective of coherent exchange rate, sufficient money supply (liquidity), exchange rate, increased output and financial openness stimulates stock market returns in Nigeria. On the basis of our findings, the government and indeed statutory capital market regulators are advised to further open up the Nigerian financial market and economy to more capital inflows needed for further economic and industrial development. Investors are also advised to hedge against stock price volatility by constructing very highly diversified portfolio's which reflects the overall market portfolio.

Karki (2018) empirically examined the macro-economic factors of the stock market performance in Nepal. It considers the annual data of four macroeconomic variables; real GDP, inflation, interest rate and broad money supply from 1994 to 2016 and attempts to reveal the relative influence of these variables on stock prices represented by 'NEPSE Index' of the Nepalese capital market. Empirical results reveal that the performance of stock market is found to respond positively to real GDP, inflation and money supply, and negatively to interest rate. More importantly, cointegrating evidence cannot be found between macroeconomic variables and stock market index which suggests that stock price movements in Nepal are not explained by the macroeconomic variables. It supports random walk hypothesis in Nepalese stock market.

Lionel, Alfa and Samuel (2020) examined the impact of capital flight on domestic investment in Nigeria between 1980 and 2017. Deploying the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) econometric methodology, the study finds that capital flight has negative and significant impact on domestic investment. In particular, the long run impact of capital flight on domestic investment (0.57) turns out to be more severe than its impact in the short run (0.27), implying that a continuous and persistent build-up of capital flight exerts a negative cumulative effect on domestic investment over time. The study further reveals that the quality of institutions in Nigeria is a disincentive to domestic investment. It therefore recommends the strengthening of institutions to rein in on the illegal outflow of capital from the Nigerian

economy in order to guarantee the availability of investible funds. The real sector of the local economy must be grown to bolster the value of the naira. This will stem the tide of capital flight and attract investments into critical sectors.

Igwemma, Egbulonu and Assumpta, (2018) confirming the deleterious effect of capital flight on the Nigerian economy, further found that looted funds, medical expenses, and foreign education were the fundamental channels through which capital flight was initiated and sustained. Usman and Arene (2014) examined the effects of capital flight on agricultural sector growth in Nigeria. They found a negative and insignificant effect on the agricultural sector. They conclude that capital flight has no direct effect on the agricultural sector; perhaps its impact is subsumed within other macroeconomic variables. On the other hand, a more narrow implication of capital flight was conducted to determine its impact on tax revenue in Nigeria. Adetiloye (2012) used the vector error correction mechanism of the ordinary least squares (OLS) regression methodology to analyze data between 1970 and 2007, finds that capital flight has negative but insignificant impact on domestic investment in Nigeria. As noted above, this finding was without basis as the capital flight variable was conspicuously lacking in the model specification, and in the reported results. Salandy and Henry (2013) examined the impact of capital flight on growth and investment in Trinidad and Tobago found evidence of a negative and significant influence of capital flight on domestic investment.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the quasi-experimental research design. This is because the variable under study cannot be manipulated or is not under the control of researcher. The study is designed after correlation or regression research methodology. Here we try to see how two or more variables can relate or influence each other.

Data Collection Method

The data were described as time series data that is information on a variable of study over the periods of one year. Data were collect secondary data for estimation from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin from 1990 – 2023.

Model Specification

$$SMP=f(RGDP, MS, IR, EXR, IFR) \quad (1)$$

To have the estimable version of above models 1 can be rewritten to have

$$SMP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RGDP + \beta_2 MS + \beta_3 IR + \beta_4 EXR + \beta_5 IFR + \mu \quad (2)$$

Where

SMP = Stock Market Performance proxy by market capitalization to gross domestic product

RGDP = Real Gross Domestic Product

IR = Interest rate

IFR = Inflation Rate

MS = Broad money supply

EXR = Exchange Rate

$\phi_0 \alpha_0$ = Constant

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = Coefficients of independent variables

μ_i = Error Term

A-Priori Expectation

Base on theories such as capital flight and empirical results examined in this study, the variables are expected to have a Negative effect on the dependent variables. The mathematical implication is stated as follows: $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4 < 0$

Econometric Analysis

Appropriate levels of analysis will be conducted, in each case ranging from the global analysis (that reveals the overall utility of the models) to analysis of relative statistics that test the hypotheses. This study applies unit root test first so as to uncover the true nature of stationary-properties of all the variables under consideration. This is necessary in order not to run into the problem of spurious regression since unit root problems are common features encountered in most time series studies. However, the simple regression model will be employed as the estimation technique for this study. Johansen and Jusellius Co-integration Test would be applied to determine the long run equilibrium of the variables in the model, while the Granger Causality Test would also be applied in checking the underlying structure of the dynamics relationship between the variables.

Ordinary least squares (OLS) are a method for estimating the unknown parameters in a linear regression model. Hutcheson (2011) defined ordinary least square (OLS) regression as a generalized linear modeling technique that may be used to model a single response variable which has been recorded on at least an interval scale. This method minimizes the sum of squared vertical distances between the observed responses in the dataset and the responses predicted by the linear approximation.

OLS technique may be applied to single or multiple explanatory variables and also categorical explanatory variables that have been appropriately coded. In single explanatory variables, the relationship between a continuous response variable (Y) and a continuous explanatory variable (X) may be represented using a line of best-fit, where Y is predicted, at least to some extent, by X. If this relationship is linear, it may be appropriately represented mathematically using the straight line equation $Y = a + \beta x$

For the multiple explanatory variables additional variables are added to the equation. The form of the model is the same as in a single response variable (Y), but this time Y is predicted by multiple explanatory variables (X₁ to X₅).

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 \tag{3}$$

The interpretation of the parameters (a and β) from the above model is basically the same as for the simple regression model, but the relationship cannot be graphed on a single scatter plot. A indicates the value of Y when all variables of the explanatory variables are zero. Each β parameter indicates the average change in Y that is associated with a unit change in X, whilst controlling for the other explanatory variables in the model. Model-fit can be accessed through comparing deviance measures of nested models. For example, the effect of variable X₃ on Y in the model can be calculated by comparing the nested models

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 \tag{4}$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 \tag{5}$$

The change in deviance between these models indicates the effect that X₃ has on the prediction of Y when the effects of X₁ and X₂ have been accounted for (it is, therefore, the unique effect that X₃ has on Y after taking into account X₁ and X₂). The overall effect of all three explanatory variables on Y can be assessed by comparing the models

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 \tag{5}$$

$$Y = a. \tag{6}$$

The significance of the change in the deviance scores can be accessed through the calculation of the F-statistic using the equation provided above (these are, however, provided as a matter of course by most software packages). As with the simple OLS regression, it is a simple matter to compute the R-square statistics.

Unit Root Test

The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test is used to test the stationarity property of a time series data in order to avoid the spurious regression problem. The ADF unit root test is specified as

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \beta Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \tag{7}$$

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \beta Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \tag{8}$$

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \beta Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \tag{9}$$

Note: The null hypothesis is rejected on the ground that the absolute value of the calculated ADF test statistic is larger than the absolute value of the Mackinnon critical value.

Cointegration Test

Cointegration is a statistical property of time series variables. In a situation where two or more series are individually integrated (in the time series sense) but some linear combination of them has a lower order of integration, then the series are said to be cointegrated. The VECM is more useful in Multivariate framework. To test for the presence of long-run equilibrium relationship, the Johansen's and Juselius (1990) and Johansen (1991) multivariate cointegration technique is employed. The cointegration test is based on the following equation.

(10)

Where α and β are 4×4 matrices and k is the lag length. The tests used here involved cointegration with linear deterministic trend in the vector auto regression (VAR).

Granger Causality Test

In conducting an econometric study, the direction of causal relationship among variables is determined according to the information obtained from the theory. In this study, Granger Causality test was used in order to test the hypotheses regarding the presence and the direction of the causality between assets quality and profitability of deposit money banks. For the purpose of this, the direction of causality determines the direction of the relationship among variables and Granger Causality test has three different directions in respect of this and they include the following:

One way causality

In a single equation model, Y is the dependent variable and X independent variable. The Granger, (1969) approach to this, is to see how much of the current Y can be explained by past values of Y and then to see whether adding lagged values of X can improve the explanation. In this case, Y is said to Granger-caused by X if x helps in the prediction of Y , or equivalently if the coefficient on the lagged X 's are statistically significant. Here, there is a causality relationship from X towards Y . Independent variable is the cause and causes a one way effect on dependent variable, which shows the presence of one-way causality and the relationship is determined as Y on X .

Two way causality

In this case of two way causality, there can be reciprocal effect between variables. In this case, X Granger cause Y and Y Granger cause X . The Statement of " X Granger cause y and y Granger cause X does not imply that Y is the effect or the result of X . what it simply means is that Granger causality measures precedence and information content but does not by itself indicate causality in the more common use of the term.

Lack of Causality

This means that there is no relationship among variables, therefore no causality. In this case, in order to apply Granger causality test, the series that belong to variables should be stationary. Therefore, it is necessary to make test, the series that belong to variables should be stationary. Gujaranti (1995) submits that recent studies have shown that the conventional F-test for determining joint significance of regression-derived parameters, used as a test of causality, is not valid if the variables are non-stationary and the test statistics does not have a standard distribution. In this study, Granger causality test would be applied in order to determine the presence of the relationship among variables and its direction. The Granger's causality test (Granger, 1969) is carried out by using the following equations:

According to Tari (2005) the equation suggests that if the addition of the information about the variables x to the model contributes to the estimate of the variables y , the variable x is the cause of the variable y . Here equation 5 shows a causality relationship from x to y and the equation 3.15 from y to x . Analyzing the model presented above, Granger causality test is carried out as $H_0: \beta = 0$ and $H_1: \beta \neq 0$ when H_0 hypotheses is accepted, X is not the cause of Y , But if H_1 hypotheses is accepted, then X is the cause of Y . If both hypotheses are rejected, this means that there is a two-way causality between X and Y . The Granger testing works in a way that, if " F " table value, H_0 hypotheses is accepted as "there is no causality from X to Y . But if " F " value is higher than the table value, H_0 hypotheses is rejected and it is causality from X to Y . All these calculations are applied in the same way in order to test whether there is causality from Y to X .

The main objective of this study is to investigate the causality between the independent and the dependent variables. Granger (1996) proposed the concept of causality and exogeneity: a variable Y_t is said to cause X_t ,

if the predicted value of X_t is ameliorated when information related to Y_t is incorporated in the analysis. The test is based on the following equation below

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_{t-1} + \alpha_2 X_{t-2} + \dots + \alpha_n X_{t-n} + \mu_{1t} \tag{11}$$

and

$$X_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Y_{t-1} + \beta_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \beta_n Y_{t-n} + \mu_{2t} \tag{12}$$

Where X_t and Y_t are the variables to be tested while μ_{1t} and μ_{2t} are white noise disturbance terms and n is maximum number of lags. The null hypothesis $\alpha_1 = \beta_1 = 0$ for all 1 's is tested against the alternative hypothesis $\alpha_1 \neq 0$ and $\beta_1 \neq 0$, if the coefficient of α_1 are statistically significant, that of β_1 are not, then X causes Y , If the reversal is true than Y causes X . However, where both coefficient of α_1 and β_1 are significant then causality is bi-directional.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section is established with the presentation and analysis of data sourced as discussed from the previous chapter.

Table 1: Test of Unit Root

Null Hypothesis: SMP has a unit root		t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic		-6.774404	0.0000
Test critical values:	1% level	-3.646342	
	5% level	-2.954021	
	10% level	-2.615817	
Null Hypothesis: RGDP has a unit root		t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic		-4.111109	0.0030
Test critical values:	1% level	-3.639407	
	5% level	-2.951125	
	10% level	-2.614300	
Null Hypothesis: IR has a unit root		t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic		-9.899394	0.0000
Test critical values:	1% level	-3.653730	
	5% level	-2.957110	
	10% level	-2.617434	
Null Hypothesis: MS has a unit root		t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic		-6.262068	0.0000
Test critical values:	1% level	-3.639407	
	5% level	-2.951125	
	10% level	-2.614300	
Null Hypothesis: EXR has a unit root		t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic		-7.150382	0.0000
Test critical values:	1% level	-3.653730	
	5% level	-2.957110	
	10% level	-2.617434	

Source: E -View 12.0

From Table 1, the results of the unit root tests show that the null hypotheses of a unit root for time-dependent variables of a non-stationary nature can be made stationary at the first difference. It also shows that all the variables in the model are integrated of order 1(1). This enable us adopt the error correction model with Johansson cointegration test. Having established the order of integration for the variables, the next step is to carry out a co-integration test to determine whether a long-run relationship exists between

the variables. In this study we adopt co-integration test developed by Johansen (1988). The result of the co-integration test is presented in table 2).

Table 2: Johansen Co-Integration Test Results

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.741451	119.3300	95.75366	0.0005
At most 1 *	0.599418	74.69184	69.81889	0.0194
At most 2	0.528056	44.50225	47.85613	0.0998
At most 3	0.296768	19.72271	29.79707	0.4418
At most 4	0.166480	8.104448	15.49471	0.4543
At most 5	0.061518	2.095225	3.841466	0.1478

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.741451	44.63812	40.07757	0.0143
At most 1*	0.599418	60.18959	33.87687	0.0195
At most 2	0.528056	24.77954	27.58434	0.1097
At most 3	0.296768	11.61826	21.13162	0.5856
At most 4	0.166480	6.009223	14.26460	0.6120
At most 5	0.061518	2.095225	3.841466	0.1478

Source: E -View 12.0

From Table 2 the results of the Johansen co-integration test shows that we adopt the alternative hypotheses of at most one co-integrating equation at the 5% level of significance. This implies that, there is one linear combination of the variables that are stationary in the long run and also confirms the existence of a long-run relationship between macroeconomic variables and performance of Nigeria stock market.

Table 3: Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
RGDP does not Granger Cause SMP	33	0.71680	0.4971
SMP does not Granger Cause RGDP		3.24909	0.0438
IR does not Granger Cause SMP	33	1.37558	0.2692
SMP does not Granger Cause IR		0.15996	0.8530
EXR does not Granger Cause SMP	33	3.67538	0.0382
SMP does not Granger Cause EXR		0.30696	0.7381
MS does not Granger Cause SMP	33	3.27926	0.0425
SMP does not Granger Cause MS		0.65826	0.5256
IFR does not Granger Cause SMP	33	2.50931	0.0994
SMP does not Granger Cause IFR		2.09632	0.1418

Source: E -View 12.0

From table 3, the results show that the F-statistic for the null hypotheses of the causality test running from stock market performance to real gross domestic product is 3.24909 with a p-value of 0.0438, the study conclude that there is unidirectional causality from stock market performance to real gross domestic product, the null hypotheses of the causality test running from exchange rate to stock market performance is 3.67538 with a p-value of 0.0382, the study conclude that there is unidirectional causality from exchange rate to stock market performance. the null hypotheses of the causality test running from money supply to stock market performance is 3.27926 with a p-value of 0.0425, the study conclude that there is unidirectional causality from money supply to stock market performance.

Table 4: Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.607007	1.270516	0.477764	0.6799
D(SMP(-1))	0.652802	0.701614	0.930429	0.4504
D(SMP(-2))	0.016467	0.374941	0.043920	0.9690
D(SMP(-3))	-0.208449	0.298494	-0.698334	0.5572
D(RGDP (-1))	0.495979	0.668916	0.741467	0.0357
D(RGDP (-2))	0.812490	0.458460	1.772217	0.2184
D(RGDP (-3))	-1.169172	0.845198	-1.383312	0.0407
D(IR (-1))	0.137734	0.133188	1.034136	0.4097
D(DS(-12))	-0.337000	0.178587	-1.887038	0.0398
D(IR (-3))	-0.122447	0.070203	-1.744190	0.2232
D(EXR(-1))	-0.855338	0.434958	-1.966484	0.0381
D(EXR(-2))	0.133128	0.689911	0.192964	0.8648
D(EXR(-3))	-0.395920	0.898852	-0.440473	0.7026
D(IFR (-1))	0.153880	0.634843	0.242391	0.8311
D(IFR (-2))	-1.229508	0.661882	-1.857594	0.0043
D(IFR (-3))	0.600599	0.556921	1.078427	0.3936
D(MS (-1))	0.085051	0.152257	0.558599	0.6326
D(MS (-2))	-0.321536	0.216025	-1.488423	0.0451
D(MS (-3))	-0.304673	0.195085	-1.561746	0.2587
ECM(-1)	-0.740750	0.547226	-0.257206	0.0011
R-squared	0.968265	Mean dependent var		0.166818
Adjusted R-squared	0.666785	S.D. dependent var		4.656176
S.E. of regression	2.687769	Akaike info criterion		4.235587
Sum squared resid	14.44821	Schwarz criterion		5.227444
Log likelihood	-26.59145	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.469238
F-statistic	11.211699	Durbin-Watson stat		0.987023
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: E -View 12.0

The parsimonious error correction result indicates a good fit with an F-ratio of 11.211699 probability of 0.000000 which implies that the model is statistically significant, an R^2 of 96.8% and an adjusted R^2 of 66.7% meaning that the model explains approximately 66.7% of the variations in stock market performance in the model, the D-Watson statistic of 0.987023 suggests absence of any autocorrelation. The error correction term of -0.740750, has the appropriate negative sign is significant and shows that approximately 74% of the deviation from long run equilibrium in the stock market performance model is corrected every year (since it is estimated annually), the findings proved that at lag one, real gross domestic product have positive and significant effect on stock market performance, interest rate have positive but no significant effect, exchange rate have negative and significant effect on stock market performance while inflation rate and money supply have positive and no significant effect on stock market performance. Empirically, the findings confirm the findings of Ndlovu, Faisal, Resatoglu and Tursoy (2018) that interest rate, money supply and inflation had positive impact on share prices, whereas exchange rate had a negative effect on stock prices, the findings of Kirui, Wawire and Onono (2014) that exchange rate had significant relationship with stock returns, while GDP, inflation and Treasury bill rates indicated an insignificant link with stock returns, the findings of Ouma and Muriu (2014) that: money supply and inflation had significant positive effect on stock market returns; exchange rate had negative impact on stock returns; while interest rate had no relationship with stock returns and the findings of Lyndon and Gbalam (2019) that a long-run equilibrium and short-run dynamic relationships existed between the selected macroeconomic variables and stock market performance in the Nigerian Stock Exchange. this finding confirm the findings of Buigut, Soi, Koskei and Kibet (2013) that debt, equity and gearing ratio were significant determinants of share prices for the sector under consideration, the findings

of Kipngetich, Kibet, Guyo and Kipkoskey (2011) that public information disclosed in the prospectus was insignificantly mirrored in initial public offer prices and that rational theory cannot explain the effect of investor sentiment in initial public offer market in Kenya given that investor sentiment and board prestige were negatively related to initial public offer price and the findings of Chkili and Nguyen (2014) that the exchange rate does not impact stock market returns of BRICS countries, regardless of the regimes and the findings of Caporale, Hunter and Ali (2014) showed also a significant causal relation from exchange rates to stock returns.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

This study examined the effect macroeconomic variables on stock market performance in Nigeria. The study used time series data from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin from 1990-2023. The study found that 66.7% of the variations in stock market performance were explained by macroeconomic variables. Real gross domestic product have positive and significant effect on stock market performance, interest rate have positive but no significant effect, exchange rate have negative and significant effect on stock market performance while inflation rate and money supply have positive and no significant effect on stock market performance. From the findings, the study concludes that macroeconomic variables have mixed effect on stock market performance.

Recommendations

- i. The study recommended the need to sustain the Central Bank's current exchange rate policies, which had resulted in the convergence of rates in the market. The recommendation was that there is the need for sensible coordination of macroeconomic policies in Nigeria. Policy a maker in Central bank needs to make such policies that help to stabilize the exchange rate.
- ii. Sufficient level of money supply through appropriate monetary policy must be put in place in order to encourage stock market activities and consequently stock prices in Nigeria.
- iii. The exchange rate as a pass-through variable for the domestic financial markets must be well managed in order to improve stock market stability. Since this study has shown the critical role of the naira exchange rate in ensuring market stability, it is clear that a stable naira regime can contribute extensively to the stability of the stock market and eventual rise in stock prices in Nigeria.
- iv. Inflation control should be brought to a level where it becomes stock market enhancing and efficient exchange rate management should be adopted by government; which take into account the relevance of the stock market as a possible significant strong economical indices; when addressing the issue of exchange rate management.
- v. Interest rates should be made to encourage investment in Nigeria, so as to enhance stock market returns. This is because an increase in investment will enhance stock market performance and the resultant rise in stock returns.
- vi. Openness of the economy to foreign capital flows should be put in place in order to stimulate stock market returns in Nigeria. However, caution should be exercised in this respect because of the possibility of destabilizing short-term capital flows.

REFERENCES

- Akani, H.W., & Lucky, A.L., (2014). Money supply and aggregate stock prices in Nigeria: An analysis of co-integration and causality test. Research Journalist. *Journal of Finance*, 2(10), 1-24.
- Aduda, J., Masila, J. M., & Onsongo, E. N. (2022). The determinants of stock market development: The Case for the Nairobi Stock. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(9), 214-227.
- Agrawal, G., Srivastav, A.K. & Srivastava, A. (2010). A study of exchange rates movement and stock market volatility. *International Journal of Business and Management*.5 (12).62-73.
- Akgun, A., EremŞahin, I. & Yilmaz, B. (2013). The effect of variations in gold and oil prices on BIST 100 Index. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*.4 (10), 1-17.

- Al-Shboul, M. & Anwar, S. (2014). Foreign exchange rate exposure: evidence from Canada. *Review of Financial Economics*. 23. 18-29.
- Al-Shubiri, F.N. (2010). Analysis the determinants of market stock price movements: an empirical study of Jordanian commercial banks. *International Journal of Business and Management*.5(10).137-147.
- Aray, H. & Gardeazabal, J. (2010). Going multinational under exchange rate uncertainty. *Journal of International Money and Finance*. 29. 1171-1191.
- Arouri, M.E.H., Lahiani, A. & Nguyen, D.K. (2024). World gold prices and stock returns in China: insights for hedging and diversification strategies. *IPAG Business school, Working Paper*. 1-20.
- Bartram, S.M. & Bodnar, G.M. (2012). Crossing the lines: the conditional relation between exchange rate exposure and stock returns in emerging and developed markets. *Journal of International Money and Finance*. 31. 766-792.
- Bartram, S.M., Brown, G.W. & Minton, B.A. (2010). Resolving the exposure puzzle: the many facets of exchange rate exposure. *Journal of Financial Economics*. 95. 148-173.
- Bello, Z. (2023). The association between exchange rates and stock returns. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*,10(3).40-45.
- Bernanke, B.S. & Kuttner, K.N. (2005). What explains the stock market's reaction to federal reserve policy? *Journal of Finance*. 60. 1221-1257.
- BIS. (2013). Foreign exchange turnover in April 2013: preliminary global results. *Monetary and Economic Department, BIS*.1-22.
- Bredin, D. & Hyde, S. (2011). Investigating sources of unanticipated exposure in industry stock returns. *Journal of Banking & Finance*.1128-1142.
- Burbidge, J. & Harrison, A. (1984). Testing for the effects of oil-price rises using vector autoregressions. *International Economic Review*.25 (2).459-484.
- Can Inci, A. & Soo Lee, B. (2024). Dynamic relations between stock returns and exchange rate changes. *European Financial Management*.20 (1).71-106.
- Caporale, G.M., Hunter, J. & Ali, F.M. (2014). On the linkages between stock prices and exchange rates: evidence from the banking crisis 2007-2010. *International Review of Financial Analysis*. Forthcoming.
- Cheluguet, J. K. (2008). *Investor's Demand for IPOs and First Day Performance: Evidence from Nairobi Stock Exchange*. Nairobi: University of Nairobi.
- Chkili, W. & Nguyen, D.K. (2024). Exchange rate movements and stock market returns in a regime-switching environment: Evidence for BRICS countries. *Research in International Business and Finance*. 31. 46-56.
- Choi, J.J. & Kim, Y. (2003). The Asian exposure of U.S. firms: Operational and risk management strategies. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*. 11. 121-138.
- Ciner, C. (2001). On the long run relationship between gold and silver prices a note. *Global Finance Journal*. 2001. 299-303.
- Ciner, C., Gurdgiev, C. & Lucey, B.M. (2013). Hedges and safe havens: an examination of stocks, bonds, gold, oil and exchange rates. *International Review of Financial Analysis*. 29. 202-211.
- Clock. (2009). Ordinary least squares linear regression: flaws, problems and pitfalls. *Clock Backward Essays*.
- Eita, J. H. (2011). *Determinants of Stock Market Prices in Namibia*. Working Paper 209 Monash University. Monash University.
- Fama, E. F. (2000). *Short-Term Interest Rates as Predictors of Inflation; The Debt Market*. Cheltenham: Elgar.
- Fama, E.F. & French, K.R. (2004). The capital asset pricing model: theory and evidence. *The Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 18(3).25-46.
- Fattouh, B. (2007). The drivers of oil prices: The usefulness and limitations of non-structural model, the demand-supply framework and informal approaches. *Oxford Institute for Energy Studies*, 5(4),1-44.

- Filis, G. (2010). Macro economy, stock market and oil prices: do meaningful relationships exist among their cyclical fluctuations? *Energy Economics*, 32. 877-886.
- Garza-Garcia, J., and Yu, Y. (2010). *International Determinants of Stock Market Performance in China: A Cointegration Approach. Working Paper 03/10*. University of West of England.
- Gatua, F. K. (2013). *Analysis of Share Price Determinants at Nairobi Securities Exchange*. Unpublished MBA Project of the University of Nairobi.
- Gogineni, S. (2010). Oil and the stock market: an industry level analysis. *The Financial Review*. 45. 995-1010.
- Hacker, R.S., Karlsson, H.K. & Mansson, K. (2024). An investigation of the causal relations between exchange rates and interest rate differentials using wavelets. *International Review of Economics and Finance*. 29. 321-329.
- Hamilton, J.D. (1983). Oil and the macroeconomy since world war II. *The Journal of Political Economy*. 91 (2). 228-248.
- Hamrita, M.E. & Trifi, A. (2011). The relationship between interest rate, exchange rate and stock price: A wavelet analysis. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*. 1(4). 220-228.
- Hood, M. & Malik, F. (2013). Is gold the best hedge and a safe haven under changing stock market volatility? *Review of Financial Economics*. 22. 47-52.
- Jahur, M. S., Quadir, S. M., and Khan, M. A. (2014). Determinants of stock market performance in Bangladesh. *Indonesian Management and Accounting Research*, 13(1), 16-28.
- Jefferis, K.R. & Okeahalam, C.C. (2000). The impact of economic fundamentals on stock markets in southern Africa. *Development Southern Africa*. 17 (1). 23-51.
- Karitie, D. W. (2010). *Long-run Performance of Initial Public Offerings: Evidence from the NSE*. Unpublished MBA Project, University of Nairobi.
- Kasman, S., Vardar, G. & Tunç, G. (2011). The impact of interest rate and exchange rate volatility on banks' stock returns and volatility: Evidence from Turkey. *Economic Modelling*. 28. 1328-1334.
- Keynes, J. M. (1930). *Treatise on Money and the General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money 1927 to 1939*. Maynardkeynes.org.
- Kilian, L. & Hicks, B. (2013). Did unexpectedly strong economic growth cause the oil price shock of 2003-2008? *Journal of Forecasting*. Forthcoming.
- Kim, K. (2003). Dollar exchange rate and stock price: evidence from multivariate cointegration and error correction model. *Review of Financial Economics*. 12. 301-313.
- Kimani, D. K., and Mutuku, C. M. (2023). Inflation Dynamics on the Overall Stock Market Performance: The Case of Nairobi Securities Exchange in Kenya. *Economics and Finance Review*, 2(11), 1-11.
- Kipngetch, T. J., Kibet, B. J., Guyo, S. A., and Kipkoskey, B. J. (2011). *Determinants of Initial Public Offer Pricing in Kenya*. London: The Centre for Innovations in Business and Management Practice.
- Korkeamäki, T. (2011). Interest rate sensitivity of the European stock markets before and after the Euro introduction. *Journal of International Financial markets, Institutions & Money*. 21. 811- 831.
- Kumar, D. (2014). Return and volatility transmission between gold and stock sectors: Application of portfolio management and hedging effectiveness. *IIMB Management Review*. 26. 5-16.
- Lardic, S. & Mignon, V. (2008). Oil prices and economic activity: an asymmetric cointegration approach. *Energy Economics*. 30. 847-855.
- Lawrence, C. (2003). Why is gold different from other assets? An empirical investigation. In *Research Manuscript*. London, UK: World Gold Council. 1-45.
- Lescaroux, F. & Mignon, V. (2008). On the influence of oil prices on economic activity and other macroeconomic and financial variables. *OPEC Energy Review*. 32 (4). 343-380.
- Maku, O. A., and Atanda, A. A. (2010). Determinants of stock market performance in Nigeria: long-run analysis. *Journal of Management and Organizational Behavior*, 1(3), 5-16.

- Martinez-Moya, P., Ferrer-Lapena, R. &Escribano-Sotos, F. (2013). Relationship between interest rate changes and stock returns in Spain: a wavelet-based approach. *Working Paper, Department of Economics and Finance, UCLM*. Spain. 1-24.
- Mehwish, Z. (2013). Determinants of Stock Market Performance in Pakistan. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 4(5), 1017-18.
- Miao, B., Zhou, S., Nie, J. & Zhang, Z. (2013).Renminbi exchange rate exposure: evidence from Chinese industries.*Journal of Chinese Economic and Business Studies*.11 (4).229-250.
- Mollick, A.V. &Assefa, T.A. (2013). U.S. stock returns and oil prices: The tale from daily data and the 2008-2009 financial crisis. *Energy Economics*. 36. 1-18.
- Moore, T. & Wang, P. (2014). Dynamic linkage between real exchange rates and stock prices: evidence from developed and emerging Asian markets. *International Review of Economics and Finance*. 29. 1-11.
- Moya-Martinez, P., Ferrer-Lapena, R. &Escribano-Sotos, F. (2014). Interest rate changes and stock returns in Spain: A wavelet analysis. *Business Research Quarterly*.23.Article in press.
- Muktadir-Al-Mukit, D. (2012). Effects of interest rate and exchange rate on volatility of market index at Dhaka stock exchange. *Journal of Business and Technology*.7 (2).1-18.
- Narayan, P.K. & Sharma, S.S. (2011).New evidence on oil price and firm returns. *Journal of Banking & Finance*. 35. 3253-3262.
- Narayan, P.K., Narayan, S. & Zheng, X. (2010). Gold and oil futures markets: are markets efficient? *Applied Energy*. 87. 3299-3303.
- Nasseh, A. & Strauss, J. (2000). Stock prices and domestic and international macroeconomic activity: a cointegration approach. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*. 40. 229-245.
- Ndatimama, E. (2008). *Performance of Initial Public Offerings: The Evidence from Nairobi Stock Exchange*. Nairobi: University of Nairobi.
- Ngugi, W. R. (2003). *Development of the Nairobi Stock Exchange: A Historical Perspective*, KIPPRA Discussion Paper No. 27. Nairobi: Kenya Institute for Public Policy.
- Ochieng, D. E., and Adhiambo, E. O. (2012).The Relationship between Macro Economic Variables and Stock Market Performance in Kenya.*DBA Africa Management Review 2012, Vol 3 No 1 pp.*, 3(1), 38-49.
- Olugbode, M., El-Masry, A. &Pointon, J. (2013). Exchange rate and interest rate exposure of UK industries using first-order autoregressive exponential garch-in-mean (egarch-m) approach. *The Manchester School*.1-56.
- Osoro, C. (2013). Investors Perspectives on the NASI AND THE NSE 20 Share Index as Performance Measurement Indicators at the Nairobi Securities Exchange in Kenya. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(18).
- Ozdemir, M. &Yesilyurt, S. (2013). The relationship between macroeconomic variables and ISE 100 Index returns during the quantitative easing policies of USD Federal Reserve: Evidence from Turkey. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*. Issue 107.130-139.
- Pierdzioch, C., Döpke, J. & Hartmann, D. (2008).Forecasting stock market volatility with macroeconomic variables in real time.*Journal of Economics and Business*. 60. 256-276.
- Rapach, D.E., Wohar, M.E. &Rangvid, J. (2005). Macro variables and international stock return predictability. *International Journal of Forecasting*. 21. 137-166.
- Rasiah, D. & Kim, P. (2011).The effectiveness of arbitrage pricing model in modern financial theory. *International Journal of Economic Research*.2(3).125-135.
- Reilly, F.K., Wright, D.J. & Johnson, R.R. (2007).Analysis of the interest rate sensitivity of common stocks.*The Journal of Portfolio Management*.33 (3).85-107.
- Ross, S.A. (1976). The arbitrage theory of capital asset pricing. *Journal of Economic Theory*.13.341- 360.
- Saborowski, C. & Weber, S. (2013). Assessing the determinants of interest rate transmission through conditional impulse response functions. *IMF Staff Papers*. January 2013. 1-36.
- Sharma, G.D. &Mahendru, M. (2010).Impact of macroeconomic variables on stock prices in India. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*.10 (7).19-26.

- Sharpe, W. F. (1964). Capital asset prices: A theory of market equilibrium under conditions of risk. *The Journal of Finance*.19(3).425-442.
- Singh, A. (1997). Stock Markets, Financial Liberalization and Economic Development. *Economic Journal*, 107(1), 771-82.
- Songole, R. K. (2012). *The Relationship between Selected Macroeconomic Variables and Stock Return at the Nairobi Securities Exchange*. Nairobi: University of Nairobi.
- Sumner, S.W., Johnson, R. &Soenen, L. (2010). Spillover effects among gold, stock, and bonds. 107-120. *Journal of Centrum Cathedra*.3 (2).106-120.
- Tangjitprom, N. (2012). The review of macroeconomic factors and stock returns. *International Business Research*. 5. 107-115.
- Yang, Z., Tu, A.H. &Zeng, Y. (2014). Dynamic linkages between Asian stock prices and exchange rates: new evidence from causality in quantiles. *Applied Economics*.46 (11).1184-1201.